

[F], Twillo [G], and OERsi [H] as well as on the discipline-specific page of forschungsdaten.info [I] makes the trainings findable. Access to the trainings as well as the underlying files is open and without registration. Interoperable file formats and a CC BY license enable reusability of the materials.

Figure 3. GitLab repository [E] with the openly accessible files of the trainings

After the cornerstones of the approach have been presented before within NFDI4ING [10], with sharing our experiences with the whole RDM community, we want to contribute to the development of open RDM trainings and foster the exchange on the approach and contents.

Resources

- [A] NFDI4ING Training Platform: <https://education.nfdi4ing.de>
Landing page with overview and access to the available trainings.
- [B] TU9 RDM Training Materials for the Engineering Sciences https://zenodo.org/communities/rdm_training_engineering_sciences/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest
- [C] Info page about NFDI4ING SIG ‘RDM Training and Education’: <https://nfdi4ing.de/training-education/>
- [D] Results of the NFDI4ING SIG ‘RDM Training and Education’ 2023/2024 Working Sessions: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15185665>
Results from the interactive sessions on an online whiteboard, published as PDF files. The whiteboard is available read-only at <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMb2X6P4=/>.
- [E] GitLab repository with RDM trainings: <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4ing/education/trainingplatform>
Provisioning of raw files for training materials, collecting feedback via Issues, versioning of trainings
- [F] Registration on Data Literacy Alliance (DALIA): *Registration of the overall training platform started, to be registered in near future*; training modules for [research data planning](#), [data collection](#), [data sharing and publication](#), [data archiving](#), and [data reuse](#) indexed in DALIA.
DALIA is a project on data literacy, including a search portal of registered OER trainings on RDM

- [G] Registration on Twillo: <https://www.twillo.de/edu-sharing/components/render/5d00f29e-85d5-4023-be2b-8f5dbcd32e66>
Portal for OER in university teaching
- [H] Registration on Open Educational Resources Search Index (OERsi): <https://oersi.org/resources?search=%22NFDI4ING+Basis+FDM+Trainings+f%C3%BCr+die+Ingenieurwissenschaften%22> (via Twillo)
Search index for OER in university teaching
- [I] Mentioning of NFDI4ING's Basic RDM Trainings at forschungsdaten.info: <https://forschungsdaten.info/wissenschaftsbereiche/ingenieurwissenschaften/>

Author contributions

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The authors would like to thank the Federal Government and the Heads of Government of the Länder, as well as the Joint Science Conference (GWK), for their funding and support within the framework of the NFDI4ING consortium. Funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) — project number 442146713.

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